

68. Availability and use of IACS geospatial data in the EU

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Gerry Lawson, (EURAF), Delia-Cristina Hristea (Planet), Michael den Herder (EFI), Kristoffer Rønn-Andersen (RegenFarmer), Sonja Kay (Agroscope), Arina Machine (Leicester Univ), Joao Palma, Ana Tomas (MVARC), Javier Corbacho (UEX)

EURAF is an NGO, based in Montpellier and Brussels (Transparency Register ID of [913270437706-82](#)). It aims “to promote the adoption of agroforestry practices across Europe by supporting efforts to develop awareness, education, research, policy making and investments which foster the use of trees on farms”. It has a network of 31 affiliated entities in 23 countries. See other Policy Briefings [here](#).

Summary

Policy Briefing #68 (v1) gives approaches to the quantification of agroforestry and woody landscape features in the EU, based upon open access to Member States' Geospatial Aid Application (GSAA) and Land Parcel Information System (LPIS) data - with harmonised coding (Lawson, Muraru & Kay 2024) of crops, land uses and environmental designations. This data will be part of a much-needed move from pixel to parcel representation of agricultural, forestry and environmental information, and should form the basis of the "Farm Sustainability Compass" promised in the DG AGRI Vision for Agriculture and Food. It should also form the core of GHG inventory reporting by Member States and the new "geospatial carbon certification registry" planned for release by 2028 through the Carbon Removals Certification Framework. Open access to anonymised IACS-GSAA-LPIS information was required of all Member States **by June 2024**, through the High Value Datasets Regulation of 21/12/22 ([2023/138](#)). This stipulated a range of publicly-collected high-value datasets, including GSAA and LPIS, which should be openly and freely available by 9.6.24, together with well documented APIs ([DG Connect 2024](#)). **Only 2 MS are fully compliant with this regulation, but 13 more are largely compliant.** EURAF hopes that compliance procedures will be initiated soon by DG CONNECT and that high-quality data will be available by the 20th anniversary of entry into law of the INSPIRE Directive on 15th May 2027. This date could also mark the launch of the "On-Farm Sustainability Compass" announced in the DGAGRI Vision for Agriculture and Food.

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1. Introduction - Progress on CAP Monitoring of Trees outside Forests

Multiple pressures on European Forests make it more important than ever to recognise the importance of **Trees outside Forests** and to ensure that they are managed not just for environmental and climate-change mitigation, but for the timber and agricultural services which they provide. A mapping system released recently by the English Forestry Commission (Figure 1) shows that 30% of the tree cover in England is outside forests. A similar situation exists in many parts of Europe but ToF has not yet been accurately mapped, and is ignored by many National Forest Inventories. This Briefing builds on several deliverables of the Horizon Europe [DigitAF Project](#):

- **Deliverable 1.1** Support for Agroforestry and Landscape Features in CAP Strategic Plans [24.6.24](#)
- **Deliverable 1.2** Database on availability of Agri-Environmental Indices in Member States at NUTS3, and options for data collection at farm scale. DigitAF EU Project. [13.12.24](#)
- **Deliverable 2.5** Plan for improvement of existing tools/models for tree and crop productivity. [2.7.24](#)
- **Deliverable 3.2** Report on the use of an interactive European map and inventory of AF products and services [25.3.25](#)
- **Deliverable 3.3** Proof-of-Concept towards a biodiversity tool for agroforestry systems. DigitAF EU Project. [9.12.23](#)
- **Deliverable 4.1** Needs and wants of DigitAF Living Labs for digital tools for agroforestry. DigitAF EU Project. [30.6.23](#)
- **Deliverable 4.5** Agroforestry tools and data catalogues: methodological approach to develop an accountable FAIRness Score. [15.5.24](#)

DigitAF Deliverable 1.2 (Kay et al. 2024) is particularly relevant since it considers which of the existing EU agri environmental indicators could be collected at parcel or farm scale, enabling an evaluation of the environmental impact of CAP agricultural interventions. The availability of agricultural and environmental data in the EU is explored in EURAF Policy Briefings 69 (Lawson, Muraru & Kay 2024) and 70 (Lawson & Muraru 2025), and in the publication *EU Agroforestry Futures* ([EURAF 2025](#)).

This Policy Briefing summarises the availability of LPIS data in EU Member States. It also describes plans in the DigitAF Project to overlay LPIS data on other datasets to estimate the area of agroforestry in Europe, following recommendations on the definition of agroforestry in EURAF Policy Briefing #15 (Lawson, Muraru, Bertomeu, et al. 2024):

1. LPIS parcels classed as "agriculture" are regarded as "agroforestry" if Copernicus Tree Cover Density (%TCD) =>5%
2. LPIS parcels classed as "agriculture" remain so irrespective of NFI or JRC "forest" designations
3. LPIS parcels classed as "forest" remain so irrespective of NFI or JRC "forest" designations.
4. Land with no LPIS parcel present is classed as agriculture (or agroforestry), forest (NFI/JRC), settlement¹, wetland² or other using the best available maps.

Following UNFCCC-LULUCF rules, land parcels can be either forest, cropland (arable and permanent crops), grassland, wetland, settlement or other. **There can be no overlap or ambiguity.** Agroforestry parcels are found on cropland and grassland; wetland and settlement agroforestry are not currently considered.

The figure of 5% TCD is recommended since this is the minimum cover threshold used in the FAO Forest Resource Assessment for the category *Other Wooded Land* (FAO 2002; FAO 2010)

Figure 1: Trees outside forests in England (forests in England have a minimum size of 0.1ha - (NCEA 2025))

¹ possibly following the Copernicus Urban Atlas, and Land Sealing products.

² possibly following the AlphaWetland project maps on Zenodo .. <https://zenodo.org/records/14745285>

1.1 The GSAA-LPIS System

All Member States (MS) maintain a CAP Integrated Administration and Control System ([IACS](#)). This has several components. One is a national or regional Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) (Zysk et al. 2020; Cetl et al. 2023) which locates all eligible agricultural land within reference parcels and calculates their maximum eligible area (MEA). Another is the Geo-Spatial Aid Application (GSAA) which contains farmers declarations of what the boundaries of eligible parcels (and sub-parcels), what they are cultivating, and animals involved³. Farmers declare their “agricultural parcels” in relation to the established LPIS “reference parcels”.

Only in a few countries, such as Spain, is the LPIS system integrated with national forest inventories (NFI) and used for Land Use Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) reporting as part of national inventories of GreenHouseGas (GHG) emissions. The LPIS is therefore not yet a comprehensive land use system. It also fails to record reference parcels for holdings which do not meet the minimum size threshold for “active farmers”, or where “hobby farmers” do not choose to apply for area payments. Member States (European Commission 2023) apply minimum payment thresholds (ranging between €100 and €500) and/or minimum holding areas (ranging from 0.3 ha to 4 ha) to decide on the definition of “active farmers”. Areas of woodland on farms may be recorded in LPIS systems, but usually only for parcels which have received an afforestation grant or a forest environment payment.

Land-use maps are complex and reflect differences in legislation, regulation and survey practices between jurisdictions. The objectives of land-use and cadastral systems tend to be the same however (Grant et al. 2020). Recently, the United Nations Committee of Experts on Global Geospatial Information Management (UN-GGIM) adopted the Framework for Effective Land Administration (FELA) (UN-GGIM 2020). This could be an ideal moment for the GSAA-LPIS to be harmonised as an **Integrated Rural Land Parcel Registry**, and linked to other initiatives like the European Land Information Service (European Commission n.d.).

The DigitAF project is building on the core conceptual model of the LPIS (Sagris et al. 2013; Sagris & Devos 2008; Inan et al. 2010) to provide parcel boundary, land use and crop data to our agroforestry modelling teams. This follows other attempts to harmonise the LPIS (Skokanová et al. 2020; Krumsteds et al. 2019; Campos-Taberner et al. 2019; Černecký et al. 2020; Dobosz et al. 2019; Campos-Taberner et al. 2023; Špulerová et al. 2022; Delgado Hernández & Valcárcel Sanz 2022; JRC 2023). In particular, the JRC report on “*Geodata and technologies for a greener agriculture in Europe*” (JRC 2023) has highlighted possibilities for new techniques to capture areas of peatland, landscape features and agroforestry from the detailed orthophotos available in LPIS Systems.

	= Agricultural parcel	< Farmer's block/ilot	< Physical block	Cadastral parcel
land use for aid scheme	one single crop group	one or several crop groups	one or several crop groups	do not match agricultural pattern
applicants	single farmer	single farmer	one or several farmers	one or several farmers
temporal aspect	annual	multi-annual	semi-permanent	land tenure cycle
main data source	farmer's application	farmer's survey	administration survey	land register/cadastre

Figure 2 categories of LPIS systems in the EU (Sagris & Devos 2008; Wiemann et al. 2013).

LPIS systems in Member States fall into four categories (Figure 2) MS with *Agricultural Parcels* and *Farmers Blocks* hold little information about forests (other than areas aided by afforestation and rural development programmes), whereas MS with *Physical Blocks* and *Cadastral Parcels* **may** contain forest information. However, availability of this data varies from country to country, and a thorough review is required of inclusion of forestry, agroforestry and landscape feature geospatial information in the LPIS of all Member States, together with assessment of actions needed for each MS to: a) fully integrate GIS systems for forestry and agriculture, and b) undertake further reconciliation with their national cadastres (including land ownership information).

³ In Ireland the "Herd Number" is used to identify farm holdings and a unique number is used even for arable farms. It is not yet apparent which MS provide a unique identifier for holdings in their public LPIS systems.

Technical Guidance on LPIS data discovery (Toth & Milenov 2020) and data sharing (Martirano & Toth 2023) is available from the EU Joint Research Centre, and use of the GSAA-LPIS is stressed in a very recent Commission Notice ([C/2025/980](#)) *Guidance on a framework for developing methodologies to monitor high-diversity of landscape features pursuant to Article 14(7) of the Nature Restoration Regulation (2024/1991)*

1.2 Farm Structure Survey

The Farm Structure Survey (FSS) takes place every 3-5 years, where using catastral records, **all farmers** are asked to record total areas and a range of land use and farm statistics (Table 1). Complete returns are made every 10 years, and intermediate FSS surveys are based on subsampling. The 2020 (100%) survey revealed 9.1 million agricultural holdings in the EU (5.3 million fewer than in 2005). This is a larger figure than for farmers receiving direct support from the CAP, which according to the DGAGRI reports *Direct payments to agricultural producers - graphs and figures* has declined from 6.3 million farms in 2019, to 6.2 million in 2020, to 6.1 million in 2021 and to 5.9 million in 2022 (DG AGRI 2022). There are therefore around 3 million farmers in the EU who do not receive agricultural payments and are not included in national GSAA-LPIS systems. **The large number of small farmers not making IACS returns should enter into land-use modelling considerations**⁴

Table 1: Areas of farmland (ha) including arable land, permanent grassland and permanent crops in the EU-27 Farm Structure Survey (FSS). Showing % “change” between 2005 and 2020 - full data [here](#).

	Farm area	UAA	Arable land	Perm grassland	Perm crops	Kitchen gardens	Unutilised agric	Wooded areas	Other areas on
2005	198,906,760	156,039,240	98,602,690	46,174,950	10,835,810	425,810	3,332,490	30,712,890	8,821,230
2007	199,537,110	157,333,230	99,068,370	46,889,610	10,982,370	392,890	2,994,680	30,460,600	8,747,700
2010	199,225,780	158,963,800	97,977,120	49,940,310	10,666,430	349,580	3,543,960	29,498,350	7,218,120
2013	195,045,590	157,254,840	97,933,440	48,769,070	10,266,850	285,770	2,533,580	28,358,480	6,897,400
2016	191,888,000	156,658,530	97,078,750	48,865,000	10,467,560	247,160	1,707,740	26,931,300	6,589,360
2020	190,382,400	157,415,700	98,094,800	47,963,700	11,138,530	205,020	2,040,320	24,092,370	6,832,800
Change%	-4.29%	0.88%	-0.52%	3.87%	2.79%	-51.85%	-38.77%	-21.56%	-22.54%

1.3 Afforestation and agroforestation metrics in the CAP

Member States differ in the way they record trees on agricultural land. They also vary in the way they report new agroforestry areas and landscape features. The CAP Strategic Plans of all Member States provide definitions and dimensions for agroforestry (Lawson 2023) and landscape features (Lawson & de Boeck 2023). Member States also report area on ha of new agroforestry (agroforestation) established annually through Result Indicator 17. This has four parts: R17.1 afforestation, R17.2 restoration, R17.3 (agroforestation), R17.4 (new woody landscape features). It is not certain that MS are providing these breakdowns since only total figures are provided. Even these show nil returns for 11 administrations. This lack of data may be the because a country plans no tree planting or because it takes place outside the CAP, following "State Aid" rules specified under the Agricultural Block Exemption Regulation (Policy Briefing #19) (Table 2).

This lack of information on agroforestry areas is regrettable given the important role that agricultural trees play in climate-change mitigation (Lawson, Kay, et al. 2023) adaptation (Lawson, Huska, et al. 2023), and environmental services (EURAF 2024)

⁴ In France, for example, it is estimated that 20% of agricultural land is not recorded in the GSAA.LPIS system. (Ceschia pers comm)

Table 2: Result Indicator 17 - Afforestation, restoration, agroforestation and woody landscape features (ha) targets - shown cumulatively in the CAP 2023-2027

Member State	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	Target value
Austria	0	0	0	200	200	200	0	200
Belgium-Flanders	0	39.74	96.62	157.24	218.87	288.99	359.11	359.11
Belgium-Wallonia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bulgaria	0	0	5.95	1719.95	1732.45	2870.14	2872.65	2872.65
Croatia	0	0	60	640	940	1178	0	1178
Cyprus	30	40	40	50	50	50	50	50
Czechia	0	650	1190	1480	1770	2060	0	2060
Denmark	0	0	781	2240	3834	5455	8253	8253
Estonia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Finland	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
France	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Germany	0	0	50	130	230	340	340	340
Greece	0	129402	138808	140988	141533	160169	160169	160169
Hungary	0	0	587	6174	11174	16174	16174	16174
Ireland	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Italy	0	990	990	3000	5000	22259	40752	40752
Latvia	0	3427	3427	4891	6771	8551	10281	10281
Lithuania	0	250	950	1700	2500	3150	3500	3500
Luxembourg	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Malta	12.5	37.5	77.5	120	165.08	207.5	250.12	250.12
Netherlands	0	37564	38264	38964	39670	40377.4	0	40377.4
Poland	0	4132	8264	12396	16528	20660	20660	20660
Portugal	0	784	44323	87882	131454	174954	212287	212287
Romania	0	1761	3529	5307	7097	8903	8903	8903
Slovakia	0	442	442	2281	3086	4691	5497	5497
Slovenia	0	0	0	60	120	180	240	240
Spain	0	802	4474	14038	24029	30826	35765	35765
Sweden	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Similarly, there are no effective metrics available at the national or international level for the area of landscape features, although Member States do provide dimensions for in their CAP Strategic Plans (Table 3)

Table 3 Dimensions and breakdown of landscape features declared by Member States in CAP Statistics (not updated from first version of all CSPs) (Lawson & de Boeck 2023)

CAP-M	Landscape feature and non productive area	AT	BEF	BEW	BG	CY	CZ	DE	DK	EE	EL	ES	FI	FR	HU	HR	IE	IT	LT	LU	LV	MT	NL	PL	PT	RO	SE	SK	SI	Sum
B151	Fallow Land	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	2	3				30
B152	Hedges or woody strips	1	1	1	1			1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	20
B152	Trees in Line		1	1	1			1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1			21	
B152	Trees in Groups/ Copses	1	1	1	1			1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	24	
B152	Isolated Trees			1	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	19
B153	Buffer Strips	1	1	1	1			1									1	1	1	1	1	1	1			1		1	1	13
B153	Field Margins (# types)		1	3	1	2	7	1	1	1	1	1	2	7	1	1	4	1	4		4		1	1	2	1			44	
B153	Forest Edge Strips - non prod		1	1	1					1	1	1					1	1											7	
B154	Ditches			1			1			1	1			1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	1				16	
B154	Streams									1											1	1							3	
B155	Small Ponds	1	1	1						1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1				15	
B155	Small Wetlands						1	1		1										1	1	1	1	1					8	
B156	Traditional Stone Walls	1						1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			1					12	
B157	Cairns	1						1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1					1			8	
B158	Terraces						1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1						y	7	
B159	Cultural Features	1		5				1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			1					13	
B160	Others			1			2	1	1			2								1	1			4	1	1			-	15
B161	Cover or catch crops (7% option)		-	-			1	-	-	-	-	1	1																3	
B162	N-Fixing Crops (7% option)		-	-			1	-	-	-	-	1	1																4	
	Total elements / sub-elements active	8	8	19	8	4	18	11	6	11	13	14	1	11	12	8	16	12	8	11	11	6	21	9	10	8	5	6	7	282
	4% Option	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	28
	3% Option	y	y	y	y			y	y	y	y									y	y			y	y					12
	7% Option	y	y	y	y	y	y			y	y	y	y	y	y	y				y	y			y	y	y	y			16
	LULUCF Regulation - threshold of "forest land" (ha)	0.05	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.3	0.05	0.1	0.5	0.5	0.3	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.1	1	0.5	0.1	1	0.25	0.5	0.3	0.25	
	Strategic Plan - max LF copse/grove size (ha)	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.3	-	?	0.2	?	?	?	0.3	-	0.5	0.5	?	-	0.3	0.3	0.5	-	1.5	0.5	0.5	0.9	-	?	0.5		
	Details of hedge width and permitted gaps?	y	y	y	y			y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y			y	y	y	y			15
	Details of permitted crown size of trees in line?		y	y	y					y				y	y	y				y	y			y	y	y	y			13
	Details of crown size of isolated trees?		y	y										y	y					y	y			y	y					8
	RED shows where the definition of "copse/grove" on agricultural land differs from the national definition the minimum size threshold for a forest block. In many countries the size threshold is not given or copses/groves are not recognised as Landscape Features																													

One available metric is CAP Result Indicator 34 - "Share of UAA under supported commitments for managing landscape features, including hedgerows and trees % (Table 4), but again MS vary considerably in the way this is reported, and some countries include payments for establishment of permanent crops like vineyards or olives.

Table 4: Planned area of CAP Result Indicator 34 “Share of UAA under supported commitments for managing landscape features, including hedgerows and trees (%)” Note that R.34 measures the share of overall UAA, not just arable land.

Member State	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	Change
Austria	7.5	7.7	8.3	8.3	8.1	“+”
Belgium-Flanders	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0
Belgium-Wallonia	<0.5	1.6	1.9	2.1	2.4	“+”
Bulgaria	1.1	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	“??”
Croatia	0.5	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	“+”
Cyprus	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	0
Czechia	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0
Denmark	1.9	1.9	1.9	1.9	1.9	0
Estonia	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0
Finland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0
France	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0
Germany	3.0	3.6	3.9	4.0	4.2	“+”
Greece	13.8	13.3	14.8	14.8	16.8	“+”
Hungary	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0
Ireland	4.7	4.7	4.7	4.7	4.7	0
Italy	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0
Latvia	0.0	0.0	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	“+”
Lithuania	2.9	2.9	2.9	2.9	2.9	0
Luxembourg	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	0
Malta	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0
Netherlands	3.0	3.6	3.6	3.6	3.6	“+”
Poland	<0.5	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	“+”
Portugal	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0
Romania	0.0	2.1	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	“??”
Slovakia	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.1	1.3	“+”
Slovenia	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.6	“+”
Spain	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0
Sweden	0.0	0.0	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	“+”

Four Member States (BE-F, FI, IT, CY) do not have any eco-schemes mapped against Result Indicator 34 (share of UAA under supported commitments to maintain landscape features) in the Catalogue of CAP Interventions, and only six MS have ecoschemes which specifically mention “landscape” in their titles. The creation of new landscape feature eco-schemes on arable land (as promised in the Simplification Regulation 2024/1469 - as a replacement for GAEC8) has therefore not happened in many Member States. Further data on this is awaited from DGAGRI. EURAF and ELO also plan to update Policy Briefing 22 (Lawson & de Boeck 2023), which recorded the dimensions of landscape features, and the way that they were mapped in GSAA-LPIS systems. Policy Briefing #70 - Lawson & Muraru (2025) give more details on landscape feature support in the CAP and the “carrot” v “stick” argument for GAEC 8.

1.4 New legislative initiatives

The Commission’s GreenData4All initiative (European Parliament 2024) was intended to evaluate the implementation by Member States of the INSPIRE Directive ([2007/2/EC](#)), and Public Access to Environmental Information Directive ([2003/4/EC](#)). It planned to “assist Europe’s green and digital transformation by updating EU rules on environmental geospatial data and on public access to environmental information”. It aimed to greater sharing of data between the public & private sectors and with the general public, and “unlock the full benefits of data sharing for data-driven innovation and evidence-based decisions”. The GreenData4All is not included in the Commission's work programme for 2025, and its future is uncertain. However, faster action is possible by enforcing compliance with the High Value Dataset Implementing Regulation ([2023/138](#)) of the Public Open Data Directive ([2019/1024](#)). This stipulated that a range of publicly-collected high-value datasets (including GSAA and LPIS) should be openly and freely available by 9.6.24, together with well documented APIs (DG Connect 2024). **At least 8 Member States do not meet these requirements (Tables 5 and 6) and a "non-compliance decision" should be issued soon by DG Connect.**

Three pieces of legislation are going through Parliament, which could make use of GSAA parcel codes

- **CRCF Regulation ([2018/841](#))** (aka “Union Certification Framework for Permanent Carbon Removals, Carbon Farming and Carbon Storage in Products”) which entered into force in December 2024 and for which a number of Delegated and Implementing acts are being developed by DGCLIMA in 2025. This specifically recommends use of GSAA parcel codes “when available”
- **Soil Monitoring Directive ([2023/0232-COD](#))**, which continues through dialogue in the European Parliament and which aims to address transboundary impacts of soil degradation, secure equal market conditions and promote policy coherence at both EU and national levels in order to deliver on its objectives regarding climate change, biodiversity, food security and water protection. This very

surprisingly makes no mention whatsoever of GSAA parcel codes, despite these being an integral part of the Farm Sustainability Tool (FaST - [DGAGRI-DGDEFIS-DGDIGIT](#))⁵

- **Forest Monitoring Regulation (2023/0413)** - which is also continuing through dialogue. EURAF has published several versions of a Briefing on this regulation, where our principal criticism is that the Regulation misses the opportunity to provide data focused on LULUCF and GHG reporting and fails to emphasise the need to integrate information on forest distribution with the CAP GSAA. An example quoted in [Policy Briefing #15](#) and Section 4 is Extremadura in Spain, where the local Forest Inventory ([ref](#)) estimates that there are 2.87 Mha of land with "forest use", the JRC Global Forest map at 10m resolution estimates that there are 968 Kha of "forest" using the FAO Forest Definition, and the Spanish GSAA-LPIS system estimates that there indeed are only 200.1 Kha of "forest" - the difference being due to land use categories of "grassland with trees" and "grassland with shrubs" - both of which receive CAP area payments and are unlikely to be forests.

2. Availability of geospatial agricultural and environmental data in Member States

2.1 Availability of GSAA and IACS Data

The EU INSPIRE Directive, obliges Member States to make geospatial data collected with public funds available in their national INSPIRE portals ([link](#)). Manual inspection of the Member States making LPIS datasets available through these portals improved significantly in 2024, but there were still 11 countries which do not meet this open data requirement for LPIS data in their INSPIRE Portals, and 11 (often different) which do not provide LPIS data through the DGAGRI agro-food geoportal ([link](#)). In total, 19 administrations from 28 provide online endpoints to harvest GSAA and LPIS data.⁶ However it is not sufficient to provide access to datafiles through the INSPIRE or DGAGRI portals. More demanding criteria are stipulated in the **High Value Datasets Regulation (2023/138)**

An [AI assisted](#) review was therefore undertaken of the MS which met the six criteria for compliance with the HVD Regulation i.e.: free of charge, full-open reuse licence, machine readable format, API access, bulk download, up to date (Table 5).

Only two countries were “**Fully Compliant**” (*AT, LU*), while 13 were “**Largely Compliant**” (*BE-W, CZ, DK, EE, FI, FR, IE, LV, NL, PT, SK, SL, SE*), 1 was “**Largely Compliant but Fragmented**” (*ES*), 6 were “**Partially Compliant**” (*BE-F, HR, CY, LT, MT, PL*), 2 were “**Highly Fragmented and Partially Compliant**” (*DE, IT*), and 4 were “**Non-Compliant**” (*BG, EL, HU, RO*).

⁵ Some MS maintain that the right to confidentiality of personal data under the GDPR regulation means that the INSPIRE Directive does not apply to soil data from IACS systems (see “[Report on the national and EU regulations on agricultural soils data sharing and national monitoring activities](#)”).

⁶ High value data, introduced by [Directive \(EU\) 2019/1024](#) (so-called Open Data Directive), are defined as data whose reuse can be associated with important benefits for society, the environment and the economy. To this end, the Directive has identified six categories (geospatial data, earth observation and environmental data, meteorological data, statistical data, business and business ownership data, mobility data). [Implementing Regulation \(EU\) 2023/138](#) specifically defined IACS agricultural and reference parcels as **being in scope** of the Open Data Directive. **Cadastral parcels** are also included. **The date for compliance with the Implementing Regulation was 9.6.24.**

Table 5 . Compliance with the six criteria of the DG CONNECT High Value Datasets Regulation (2023/138)⁷ (See Annex I, Section 3, for full details and references)

Member State	Data Holder (Paying Agency)	Free of Charge	Licence	Machine-Readable Format	API Access	Bulk Download	Up-to-Date	Overall Assessment
Austria	Agrarmarkt Austria (AMA)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Fully Compliant
Belgium (Flanders)	Agentschap Landbouw & Visserij	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Non-Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant
Belgium (Wallonia)	Organisme Payeur de Wallonie	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Bulgaria	State Fund Agriculture	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant
Croatia	Agency for Payments in Agriculture, Fisheries and Rural Development (APPRRR)	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant
Cyprus	Cyprus Agricultural Payments Organization (CAPO)	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Non-Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant
Czechia	State Agricultural Intervention Fund (SZIF)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Denmark	Danish Agricultural Agency	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Estonia	Agricultural Registers and Information Board (ARIB/PRIA)	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Finland	Finnish Food Authority	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
France	Agence de services et de paiement (ASP)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Largely Compliant
Germany	Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL) & 16 Länder Agencies	Partially Compliant	Non-Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Highly Fragmented & Partially Compliant
Greece	Payment and Control Agency for Guidance and Guarantee Community Aid (OPEKEPE)	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant
Hungary	Hungarian State Treasury	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant
Ireland	Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Italy	Agency for Payments in Agriculture (AGEA) & Regional Bodies	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Non-Compliant	Highly Fragmented & Partially Compliant
Latvia	Rural Support Service (LAD)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Lithuania	National Paying Agency (NMA)	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant
Luxembourg	Service d'Economie Rurale (SER)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Fully Compliant
Malta	Agriculture and Rural Payments Agency (ARPA)	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Non-Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant
Netherlands	Netherlands Enterprise Agency (RVO)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Poland	Agency for Restructuring and Modernisation of Agriculture (ARMA)	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant
Portugal	Institute for the Financing of Agriculture and Fisheries (IFAP)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Romania	Agency for Payments and Intervention in Agriculture (APIA)	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant
Slovakia	Agricultural Paying Agency (PPA)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Slovenia	Agency for Agricultural Markets and Rural Development (ARSKTRP)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Spain	Fondo Español de Garantía Agraria (FEGA) & 18 Regional Bodies	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant but Fragmented
Sweden	Swedish Board of Agriculture	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant

⁷ MS were expected to report on their implementation of the HVD Regulation by February 9, 2025, and every two years thereafter. See Annex I for further details of

2.2 Availability of LPIS crop and land use codes

DigitAF is maintaining a list [here](#) of crop codes, land-use codes, and meta-references used in Member States. The [LAMASUS Project](#) and other Horizon projects are helping the [EuroCrops](#) project to maintain a GitHub list of national crop codes and their mapping through the common [HCAT3 code](#). This has crop codes have been added for AT, BE-F, BE_W, CZ, DE (BB, IS, NRW), DK, EE, ES, FI, FR, HR, IE, LT, LV, NL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK (19)

Missing countries in HCAT3 are therefore BG, CY, EL, HU, IT, LU, PL, MT (8) But information does seem to be available for LU ([link](#) and [link](#)), HU - APSIS system ([link](#)), and IT (Veneto). There also seem to be companies like [Agroptima](#) which provide a paid service for LPIS data. EUROSTAT also maintains a list of [179 crop codes](#), used in their Farm Structure Survey for all farmers in their periodic surveys. These codes may be useful as an additional cross-mapping layer to HCAT3, although there are concerns that some of the HCAT3 codes are rather old, and are not useful for agroforestry (which shares the same code as forestry)..

2.3 Availability of LPIS environmental and farming constraint designations

Farmers may be limited in their opportunities to plant trees by **environmental designations** like Natura 2000 or nitrate sensitive zones. They may have access to additional CAP funds if their land is designated an Area of Natural Constraint (previously Less Favoured Areas). Environmental designations are summarised [here](#). Some countries include this information in LPIS data - all should.

Information on environmental Indicators and the degree to which information could be calculated and held at parcel-scale is given in Deliverable 1.3 (Kay et al. 2024) and EURAF Policy Briefing #69 (Lawson, Muraru & Kay 2024). Table 6 gives a summary:

Table 6 Impact Indicators which could be recorded at farm and parcel scale (Lawson, Muraru & Kay 2024)

No	Index	Comment
I.10	Greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture:	Uses national GHG emission calculations which vary greatly and are usually published only at a national level (NUTS 0). Only a few MS estimate the impact of woody vegetation outside forests separately.
I.11	Soil organic carbon in agricultural land	Based on the LUCAS soil survey therefore not available at farm or parcel scale. Averaged to NUTS2
I.12	Sustainable production of renewable energy from agriculture and forestry	Indicator is published at national (NUTS 0) scale
I.13	Soil erosion by water	Scale is different between countries. Usually only published at regional scale (NUTS2)
I.14	Ammonia emissions from agriculture	Based on manure management and fertilisation, but doesn't include the effect of ammonia sorption by agroforestry. Published only at national scale (NUTS 0)
I.15	Gross nutrient balance (N,P) on agricultural land (kg N & P/ha/yr) all MS.	Reports separately for the potential threat of nitrate and phosphorus on arable land and groundwater. Reports separately for cropland, grassland and permanent crops, but again availability is at the NUTS 0 level, and not for
I.16	Nitrates in groundwater	Reports percent of water stations with nitrate concentration over 50mg/l (per Directive 91/676/EEC) - frequency of sampling and the density of the monitored stations vary from country to country, as does the number of sampling stations over the years. May be published at river basin level.
I.17	Water Exploitation Index +	Reports % of water use over the renewable water resources available), only available at national level, or sometimes for river basins.
I.19	Increasing farmland bird populations.	Available at country (NUTS 0) level only. Species basket differs between countries, although a weighted EU basket exists. Most species will benefit from hedgerows and trees but other species (e.g. skylark and lapwing) prefer open land - therefore a less integrated index is needed.
I.20b	Percent of species and habitats of community interest related to agriculture with stable or increasing trends	Only available at NUTS 2/3 level and relates to broad habitat types
I.20a	Percentage of pollinator species of community interest related to agriculture with stable or increasing trends	Only available at NUTS 2/3 level
I.21	Agricultural land covered with landscape features	Currently only available at NUTS 3 (province) level based on LUCAS data from the JRC, or for woody landscape features based on Copernicus from the EEA

3. Use Corine land cover data overlaid on Copernicus 100m tree-cover density data

The first version of the EFI "tree desert" map was published in the 2020 EURAF Policy Briefing #2 (den Herder et al. 2020). EFI and Planet Inc. repeated the process using the 2018 rather than 2015 Copernicus TCD 100m dataset - see EURAF Press release ([Feb 2024](#)) (Figure 3). This used only the Corine codes for **arable land and permanent grassland**, and excluded permanent crops like olives and orchards. It also ranks countries according to their Tree Cover Density (TCD) (Table 7)

The COPERNICUS "[small woody feature](#)" product was not used since the "woody mask" is manipulated in several ways and excludes tree-blocks greater than 0.5ha, irrespective of the forest definition used in national laws, UNFCCC reports and in the designation of CAP landscape features.

Figure 3. Tree cover density (% tree cover in 100 m pixels) in cropland/grassland in the 39 EEA countries. The deep red areas are priority planting areas where tree cover density is particularly low. They are usually on mineral soils where agroforestry will make the greatest contribution to carbon sequestration. Copernicus tree cover density 2018 superimposed on CORINE agricultural land 2018. Each pixel in this map covers 1ha. (Lawson, Kay, et al. 2023)

Table 7: Zero-tree-index ranking of EU Member States (i.e. % agricultural hectares with zero trees) (Lawson, Kay, et al. 2023)

	PT	SE	SI	IE	FI	LV	AT	FR	DE	LU	EE	BE	IT	DK	ES	PL	CZ	HR	SK	NL	EL	HU	BG	LT	RO	CY	MT
TDI	48.0	49.4	53.5	59.1	59.5	61.7	61.9	62.4	64.0	64.9	65.1	65.3	67.3	70.1	70.1	70.2	71.2	71.4	71.4	75.2	76.1	77.7	79.3	81.8	82.2	87.9	95.2
#	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27

More detailed studies in Finland have shown that much of the tree cover attributed to agricultural land in Figure 3 is due to the overlap of 100m pixels between forest and agricultural land. This is not a disadvantage since it still shows the mosaic of small areas of forest in countries like Finland. **However it has been decided not to repeat the Corine versus TCD data using the Copernicus 10m dataset, since the minimum mapping unit of Corine is 25ha, which is inadequate to use with the detailed Copernicus product.**

A separate exercise excluded Natura-2000 land. Maps are also available as interactive [NUTS3 averages](#) (Figure 4), where the tree cover on agricultural land can be interrogated for each “county”. This data allowed a ranking to be produced of Member States with most “tree-deserts” on agricultural land. This gave the fewest tree-deserts in Portugal, Sweden and Slovenia and most in Romania, Cyprus and Malta (Table 7). Countries with the lowest area of “tree-deserts” are those with the greatest area of agroforestry (Lawson, Muraru, Bertomeu, et al. 2024).

Figure 4: Tree deserts in Europe at NUTS3 ("county-province") level. Darker areas have fewer trees.

4. Use of LPIS data overlaid on EU-JRC EU Deforestation Regulation maps of “forest”

The EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR) ([2023/1115](#)) comes into effect on 30/12/2025, having been delayed for 12 months to allow more time to implement the necessary procedures and maps. It imposes strict rules on all companies wishing to place affected products on the European market, or to export them. It also applies to all EU Member States. Products must be deforestation-free, produced in accordance with relevant local legislation, and covered by a due diligence statement (with geospatial location information). Products covered are: cattle, cocoa, coffee, oil palm, soya, wood, and rubber. **Agroforestry areas are explicitly excluded from these requirements.** DigitAF and a related project called DISTENDER therefore undertook a detailed comparison of the EU-JRC map of “forest” in the Spanish region of Extremadura with the LPIS (SIGPAC) map of agricultural and forestry parcels. The two datasets were compared at 10m pixel resolution, showing that only 20% of “forest land” shown in the EU-JRC map was shared with the LPIS data (Figure 5 and Table 8).

Figure 5: Areas of "forest" identified by the JRC "Forest Observatory" in the Spanish region of Extremadura (colours) and "non-forest" (gray). matching the data shown in Table 8

Table 8 Area (ha) identified as "forest" in the EU Forest Observatory for Extremadura and the distribution of this total forest area (968,437 ha) between 5 Land Use categories identified in the Spanish Land Parcel Identification System (SIGPAC)

Uso de Suelo (ha)	JRC Bosque	JRC No Forestal	Total
SIGPAC Bosque	200,902	79,607	280,509
SIGPAC Pastizal con árboles (PA)	401,975	748,305	1,150,280
SIGPAC Pastizal con arbustos (PR)	204,386	580,468	784,854
SIGPAC Pastizal (P5)	14,392	398,161	412,553
SIGPAC Otros (combinados)	146,782	1,388,441	1,535,224
Total	968,437	3,194,983	4,163,421

Uso de Suelo (%)	JRC Bosque	JRC No Forestal	Total
SIGPAC Bosque	20.7%	2.5%	6.7%
SIGPAC Pastizal con árboles (PA)	41.5%	23.4%	27.6%
SIGPAC Pastizal con arbustos (PR)	21.1%	18.2%	18.9%
SIGPAC Pastizal (P5)	1.5%	12.5%	9.9%
SIGPAC Otros (combinados)	15.2%	43.5%	36.9%
Total	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

This 5-fold difference between estimates of "forest land" reinforces the need for the the EU to have a reliable land use registry system - e.g. an extended LPIS - where the boundary between forest and agricultural land can be accurately reported on a parcel by parcel basis (Lawson, Muraru, Bertomeu, et al. 2024)

The Portuguese Partner in DigitAF (MVARC pers comm) is working with the JRC 10m forest map, overlaid LPIS data and LULUCF codes as follows:

1. **Forest Land** = JRC forest minus LPIS agriculture mask, minus settlement mask
2. **Cropland** = LPIS codes held separately for annual and permanent crops (woody)
3. **Grassland** = LPIS codes for permanent grassland (>5 years from ploughing)
4. **Settlements** = [Urban Atlas](#) / [Copernicus Soil Sealing](#) after extracting LPIS agric codes?
5. **Wetland** = Use national maps of GAEC2 (peatland) areas .. available for all MS?
6. **Other** = Land not covered by other categories (mainly mountains)

These maps will be added in V2 of this document

5. Use of LPIS data overlaid on Copernicus 10m tree-cover density data.

Arina Machine (a PhD student University of Leicester associated with the DigitAF project), has been using Corine 10m TCD data and LPIS to estimate areas of TOF in Extremadura. The LPIS in Spain (SIGPAC) has the great advantage of fully integrating forest and agricultural areas, and is used for LULUCF calculations. Preliminary work in Extremadura mapping frequency of different %TCD categories in the main land use classes (e.g. grassland with trees, grassland with scrub, grassland). The effect of selected %TCD cutoff for the definition of "agroforestry" (e.g. 5% v 10%) can be evaluated in this way (Figure 6, Figure 7).

Figure 6. Areas of cropland, forest and grassland in Extremadura obtained by overlaying Copernicus %TCD data and LPIS pixel information, corrected for the area of each pixel and showing the extent of high tree crown covers on permanent grassland pixels, and on cropland - where this is largely explained by permanent crops of fruit-tree species.

Figure 7 Overlay of LPIS (SIGPAC) agricultural and forest land in Extremadura with Tree Cover Density thresholds matching Figure 3. Arina Machine, PhD Thesis work. This is comparable to Figure 5, which directly maps the LPIS (SIGPAC) land use codes.

6. Development of an LPIS Aggregation Tool

The DigitAF partner Regenfarmer has developed a [LPIS Aggregator](#) web-viewer to allow inspection of LPIS data for multiple Member States. So far, information has been included from 10 administrations: AT, CZ, FR, BE-FL, NL, DK, IE, FI, DE (NS, BB), PT (Figure 8). Zooming to individual parcels is possible, giving details on the area, land use and crop codes in each parcel. It is intended to release the Aggregator by June 2025.

In some Member States boundary features like hedges or windbreaks (called “woody landscape features”) are recorded in a separate LPIS GIS layer. This was called the Ecological Focus Area (EFA) Layer in the previous CAP (Luketić et al. 2015). In the present CAP it is possibly called the “Landscape Feature Layer”, and may be used by some MS to record CAP Impact Indicator 21 (“Area of Landscape Features”). In most Member States this layer is being incorporated in the main Land Use layer of the LPIS, but this remains to be confirmed-

Figure 8. DigitAF [LPIS Aggregator](#). Hovering on parcels provides location, area, land use and crop codes, Other countries will be added as stable data and licence information becomes available.

7. Techniques used by Member States to map and include GHG emissions from ToF

In their annual UNFCCC reports Member States are obliged to map land use changes and emissions from the six LULUCF land uses:

1. **Forest Land** - using national thresholds for forest minimum area, crown cover and tree height
2. **Cropland** - including agroforestry where appropriate and separating annual and permanent crops
3. **Grassland** - using the national definitions of grassland
4. **Settlements** - using national definitions
5. **Wetland** - using national definitions
6. **Other** - which is land not covered in the other categories and is mainly land with little vegetation

An initial comparison of methods used by Member States to monitor woody vegetation in cropland and grassland in GHG reporting has been drafted ([v1 2.5.24](#)) but needs to be extended. There are also differences between Member States in the way that wildfires are reported,⁸ which are important because of the role of agroforestry in reducing fire risk and intensity ([Damianidis et al. 2020](#))

Trends in the areas of the six LULUCF “lands”, reported in the most recent UNFCCC report ([2023](#)) of the EU, compared to the base year of 1990 are: Settlements (+25%), Croplands (-8%), Forest land (+5%), Grassland (-4%), Wetlands (1%), Other lands (-5%) (Figure 9).

Figure 9 Changes in areas of the six EU LULUCF Lands in since base year of 1990 ([EU Commission 2023](#))

8 Use cases for integrated maps of trees on agricultural parcels and forest-parcels

The integrated mapping of forest and agricultural parcels will probably be easiest in those countries where the LPIS is already based on Cadastral Parcels (ES, IT, PL) or Physical Blocks (NL DK, SE, EE, HU, RO, GR).

In addition to CAP Monitoring⁹, five **use cases** are considered

1. Farm-scale models of greenhouse-gas-emissions and changes in response to nature-based mitigation solutions - in conjunction with relevant Horizon projects such as DigitAF and Reforest)
2. Landscape feature mapping in relation to the EU Nature Restoration Regulation
3. Developing tools to model catchment-hydrology and flood amelioration processes for integrated agricultural, agroforestry and forest land in river catchments.

⁸ Greece, for example, is the only Member State which reports “un-managed forest” - from which no GHG emissions have to be reported - surely a loophole which needs to be closed?

⁹ Article 68 of Regulation 2021/2116 obliges Member States to identify "non-agricultural areas considered eligible for CAP area payments.

4. Planning forest grazing (forest land) and wood pasture (agricultural land) for wildfire mitigation.
5. Contributing to a definitive parcel-scale map of EU “forests” which removes agroforestry parcels from eligibility for the EU Deforestation Regulation

8.1 Farm-scale models of GHG emissions and national LULUCF/AFOLU reporting in the EU

Much interest and activity has been generated by the EU Certification Framework for Carbon Removals (CRCF) (DGCLIMA 2023) and carbon farming generally (Kay et al. 2023). Recently, DG CLIMA has published a consultancy report on options for an Emissions Trading Scheme (AgriETS) (Bognar et al. 2023) to span both agriculture and forestry - where the main option involves the calculation of emissions for fields and farms. GHG calculations on this scale need easy access to detailed land-use information, NOT the broad-brush land-cover approximations available from systems like LUCAS (4km² points - [link](#)) or Corine (25ha mapping unit - [link](#)). The extent and boundaries of all fields on a farm must be available for emission estimation, together with predictions of the impact of Nature-based Solutions (e.g. agroforestry). It is necessary to extend the CAP Land Parcel Information System used in each Member State to include forestry parcels, and also agricultural parcels which are too small to receive payments, or which have been abandoned by their owners. DigitAF is investigating this possibility, together with national administrations. Widening the use of the existing CAP-LPIS to all rural areas (i.e. the AFOLU-LPIS) will provide the basis of the "geospatial carbon removals registry" envisaged for 2028 in the Carbon Removals Certification Framework Regulation ([2024/3012](#)). The AFOLU-LPIS will provide a) a link to national "wall to wall" UNFCCC reporting of emissions specified in the LULUCF Regulation [2023/839](#) (Bertaglia 2015) and b) give an opportunity include environmental designations Corine and other AgriEnvironmental metrics like those from MAES (Maes et al. 2020) into a single parcel-based system which can be used for CAP, NRR (qv) and GHG reporting.

Policy Relevance: LULUCF Regulation, CFCR Regulation, and possible upcoming AFOLU-Emission Trading Scheme (DG CLIMA). National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs¹⁰), Adaptation Plans and Strategies, national Nature Restoration Plans.

8.2 Landscape Feature mapping for the Nature Restoration Regulation

The biodiversity indices proposed for agricultural land in the Nature Restoration Regulation ([2024/1991](#)) include broad-scale butterfly and bird counts, which are hard to record at plot scale and two indices which could be recorded at this fine-scale. These indices are for "landscape feature area" and the organic matter content of mineral soils (Reed et al. 2014; Alliance Environnement 2019). The EU DigitAF project has used Copernicus 100m tree cover density data together with Corine grassland and cropland codes to come up with a "tree-desert-index" of areas where new agroforestry planting should be prioritised. This is the basis of the EURAF maps of tree-planting priority areas in Europe (Figures 3 and 4).

There is much more to be done to improve this index at an EU level, and DigitAF intends to replace the 100m Copernicus Tree Cover Density product with the 10m version and to use LPIS data rather than Copernicus. Again, an "integrated rural land-parcel-registry" would greatly facilitate this move to land-diversity mapping and potential CAP "payment by results" schemes.

Policy Relevance: CAP Monitoring and Nature Restoration Regulation Monitoring - e.g. there is currently no plan at Commission level to monitor “Landscape Features”, without going back to the very broad-brush LUCAS system.

8.3 Mapping tree-planting for flood mitigation, reduced soil erosion and reduced nutrient runoff.

Here again, the detailed information at farm-scale available from the LPIS, particularly if extended to include forest land, can be used for catchment and sub catchment modelling using (for example) a QGIS interface for SWAT models (Kreig et al. 2019). Tree planting on contours, together with berms/swales, can act as green barriers and

¹⁰Note the comments made by DGCLIMA ([18/12/23](#)) on the current state of NECPs in the Land Sector (i.e. agriculture and forestry combined): ***"The majority of the draft updated NECPs do not show sufficient ambition and action on land. Very few Member States show a concrete pathway to reach their national net removal targets, or sufficient actions to assist farmers, foresters and other stakeholders in building sustainable business models in line with these targets. The aggregation of the LULUCF projections shows that the overall net removals would still lead to a gap of around -40 to -50 Mt CO₂ eq. compared to the 2030 target of -310 Mt CO₂ eq... Almost all Member States need to improve their monitoring, reporting and verification to ensure the robustness and policy integration enhancements of the revised legislation. Biodiversity, nature restoration and nature-based solutions should be better integrated in the plans, to enhance carbon sinks and resilience..***

increase infiltration of water into the soil and absorption of excess nutrients in perennial vegetation. It could be extended to design rows of trees in herring-bone or Keyline design patterns to divert flood-waters to areas where they do less damage. This tool would be available for river basin planners and others who are developing solutions to increase rainfall infiltration in upper catchments and designing flood control measures in lower catchments.

Policy Relevance: National Adaptation Plans and Strategies, Water Framework Directive, Floods Directive, EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change.

8.4 Mapping agroforestry as buffer-zones around forests for wildfire mitigation

Goats, sheep, cattle, horses and pigs can be introduced carefully into fire-breaks or thinned sub-parcels in established forests, and managed in a way to reduce the volume of dead branches and shrubs on the forest floor (Bertomeu et al. 2022; Lasanta et al. 2018). This greatly decreases the intensity and risk of propagation of fires. Access to a fully integrated land use system (LPIS) that shows both forest parcels and nearby agricultural parcels with tree-cover (e.g. parkland, Dehesa and Montado) would greatly facilitate the planning of fire response and grazing agreements with local shepherds.

Policy Relevance: LULUCF Regulation and possible upcoming AFOLU 2040 Net Zero target, EU Forest Strategy, EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change, National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs).

8.5 Separating agroforests from forests in the EU Deforestation Regulation

Information currently used to evaluate "deforestation" and "degradation"¹¹ under the EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR) is based on the very broad brush FAO definition of "forest land" and is largely based entirely on Copernicus estimates of forest cover, rather than individual national definitions of forest, or national inventory reports of emissions which used definitions of forest based on the EU LULUCF Regulation or the UNFCCC Marrakesh Accord (2002). Consolidating the national rural land-parcel-registries and integrating them with land use information in LULUCF and NFI datasets would greatly improve the accuracy of estimates of "deforestation" (see EURAF Policy Briefing #15)¹². At the very least, an error analysis should be done of the changes involved in using the FAO forest definition rather than one based on national definitions and the rural land-parcel registry (i.e. national LPIS systems).

Policy Relevance: Primarily to improve data used in the EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR), but also to ensure compliance between data used for emissions reporting under the LULUCF Regulation (2018 as amended in 2023) and the Emission Sharing Regulation (2018), and also data reporting in the CAP Strategic Plan Regulation - for example areas of woody Landscape Features on agricultural land.

¹¹ According to the EUDR "forest degradation" means "structural changes to forest cover, taking the form of the conversion of primary forests or naturally regenerating forests into plantation forests or into other wooded land, and the conversion of primary forests into planted forests (Article 2 - 7)". This is **very difficult** to gauge from remote sensing alone.

¹² See this joint statement by EU timber producers and importers

<https://www.intergraf.eu/policy/policy-positions/item/578-clarifying-the-role-of-geolocation-data-in-eudr-compliance>

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